

Green Product Purchase intention in Malaysia

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify the key factors influencing green product's purchase intentions of the population of Malaysia, specifically in the town of Petaling Jaya in the state of Selangor. It also aim to enhance the relationship between green product purchasing intention and its antecedents such as price, quality and advertisement. The research design chosen for this research is quantitative and data were collected from 150 respondents residing in same state through questionnaires survey.

The statistical results showed that Without existence of environmental knowledge as moderator variable, there are no relationship between independent variables and dependent variables (perceived price, perceived quality and advertisement endorsement) and dependent variable (green products purchasing intention). The research proved that environmental knowledge play a significant role in moderating the relation between price and purchase intention, quality and purchase intention and advertisement and purchase intention.

Keywords: Consumer Purchase Intention; Perceived Price; Perceived Quality; Advertising Endorsement.

1. Introduction

According to United Nations Department of Public Information 1997, there is not an issue for the global environmental concern in the world and it is getting human attention since 1970. In addition, the concerns have pulled the greenlight of the academic researchers and become a critical discuss topics in the world today. Environmental issues such as air pollution, water pollution, ozone depletion, acid rains, overpopulation, global warming and hazardous waste had caused a significant rising in environmentalism emerged in the western Europe and US. The consumer's behavior towards environmental friendly green product can be affected by the rising of the environmental awareness in the public. Therefore, after 1970s, it leads to the beginning of the green product revolution in order to get rid of the further destroy to the environment (Alwitt and Pitts, 1993 and Elham and Nabsiah, 2011).

Environmental marketing or green marketing is referred as the all activities are designed to facilitate and create the exchange intended in order to satisfy human needs, to cultivate the high level of satisfaction of the, therefore with the lesser destruction impacts on the natural resources in the world (Polonsky, 1994). According to Shrikanth and Raju (2012), green marketing is also referring to the holistic marketing concept where the marketing and production use disposable product and services which are less harmful to the environment to prevent the implications such as non-biodegradable solid waste, global warming, water pollution, air pollution and others dangerous impact of pollutants released etc.

According to Savale, Sharma &Patil, consumer and marketer are becoming more concern about the clean environment and there is a high potential and opportunity to emerge into green product and service environment today. In addition, to establish a green product and service environment may be costly for the beginning, but the cost of product will be brought down in the future due to effective economy of scale. This research study the factors of consumers green product purchase intention where will benefits marketer and academician. However, there are several researches conducted the influences of green products toward consumer purchase intention, but demand and attitudes on green product is likely to be different across market segment and market cultures Ottman, 1992a, b).

According to Nejati and Nejati (2010) addressed that green product purchase intention can be defined as the consumer's behavior of purchasing item or product that are environmentally friendly from the perception of consumer. The authors also further explain that consumer's observation and practices in purchase green product also can minimize the negative

environmental impact through the reduction of energies consumption, protection of natural environment and resources and to improve safety and healthy.

Some of the scientists and researchers found that there are a lot of adverse effects produced by the Mother Nature as a result of artificial products and interventions, the world are gradually to realize the dangerous environmental impacts of irresponsible manufacturer and poor living habits today. According to Tehrani, Sinha (2011), there are some awareness green product campaigns and educational programmes held in order to carry out on the subject of environmental sustainability, to increase the awareness of consumer toward green products.

Madu (2001) found that the influence of advertisement able to encourage green effort and green living to successfully draw consumers' attention to green products. In addition, his research shows the existing market for green product is still relatively new but with huge potential to grow in future. In order to fully implement green product to the consumers, it is a need to study consumers purchase intention and their decision on the green product. Moreover, the factors influence the green product purchase intention are positively correlated with the consumers' level of confidence toward the source from which the product is derived (Vazquez-Brust and Sarkis, 2012). According to Moreo (2008) and Madu (2001), to influence green product purchase intention, it is important to make sure that consumers are well-educated and understand the green product, its origin and the authenticity of its contents.

2. Literature Review

According to Lee, Ling, Yeow and Hasan (2011), green product is defined as a product that is designed or attributed, by using recycle resources, which will benefit the natural environment and reduce the toxic effect toward the natural environment on its entire life-cycle. According to Rezai (2010), who states different perspective for the definition of green product and mentions, that green product is referred to the product that is not a threat to the natural environment, does not deplete any natural resources, and can be recycled and has re-usable packaging or non-toxic materials.

Moreover, Enviro News & Business says that green product is the product that produces less of impact to the surrounding and the natural environment, and less damaging to human health. A further explanation on green product by Enviro News & Business states that green product is formed by part of recycled component, and manufactured component in a more energy-conservative method and will be supplied to the market with lesser packaging.

Another definition of green product explained by Department of the Treasury in the United States of America (2009) and mentioned that green product or service comprised of water-efficient product, recycled content product and product that inherent with the lowest watt stand-by power, alternative fuel, environmentally preferable product, alternative fuel vehicle and hybrid, renewable energy, non-ozone depleting substances, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and other designated items which contain recovered materials.

According to Dobson and Lucardie (2002) mention that the term of green where do not has relationship with shade, however the name of green is the decision in fitting on the grounds that green is a colour that is basically related with nature. Green product item is viewed as a kinder to the earth compared with non green product, in somehow. The term is widely used and it does not take much for an item to be called green, so it can blanket an extensive variety of customer product. An item is considered earth accommodating in the event that it is biodegradable, implying that it will represent no risk to the earth nature's turf, when it is discharged to the water, air or earth while being used or when discarded. This sort of item typically decays much faster in a landfill, compared with comparative things that are not biodegradable. Biodegradable families are from unit cleaner, cleanser, dish and dishwasher cleanser and clothing cleanser and so on. These are simply a couple of cases of this sort of green items.

According to Wilson and Piepkorn (2013), based on the off chances that an item holds any measure of recycled product in its development, it is addition view as green for two reasons. This can be explained on re-using and re-utilizes a material, keeping it out of the landfill, and spares on nature's turf when elective materials are not produced and utilized for that part. An item has been extensively decreased compared with other comparative item where obliging less transporting room and thus decreasing carbon emanation throughout transport to market, it may be viewed as green. In addition, an extraordinary stride has been made to fabricate green item to decrease the assembling process and reduce the effect on the earth, and making them earth-accommodating related to usage and transfer. A lot of nations, states and areas likewise have set up green activity to urge organization to look for approaches to make green item more earth-accommodating. For every exertion, even those that may seem small for us, we must help to diminish the effect buyer merchandise on nature. A not needed or not required gift that is gifted again to someone else is likewise viewed as green in light of the fact that the thing is spared from landfill or waste, and an alternate thing does not need to be produced for the gift. Gifting defined as picking up prevalence with the individual who has adoration to reuse or basically need to better deal with their gift plan. For the producer is well mindful of the interest of green item and need to attract their wares, which they typically consider to be the best green item. Nonetheless, shopper will ought to peruse names to affirm before purchasing to guarantee they are getting what they pay for, and it is simply to put the expression of green on any item. We have to remember that green item is not the carbon zero or carbon impartial item which is indeed greener, however there may be resemblance. Green also can be applied to facility and procedure. Green activity attempts in an

exertion to attract the need to be a kinder to the surrounding in all that a person work. Green activity and green product are different; however there is a sort of connection for both.

According to Preston (2009) shows that the eco accommodating item defined as the item that do not destroy nature environment, whether in their utilization, generation or transfer. When using the developing environmental awareness item, it will help to monitor vitality, minimize carbon foot shaped impression, outflow of nursery gasses, and does not prompt contamination to the earth. Therefore, these do not destroy nature's turf or affect the environmental when they are discarded. There are some extra eco inviting items that made from reused materials. This reuse item will help to decrease the requirement for new crude material and the measurement of waste will be sent to landfill that waste could be redirected to making recycled item. Thus, interest for these reuse items will help to finish the reusing circle, and manage the reusing business. Thus, the eco cordial item could extend from eco friendly dress, naturally agreeable family cleaning item, and eco gifts that can be given to the friend and family.

According to Vasil (2012) shows that the strides making and eco accommodating utilization toward environmental friendliness item is an important venture to make sure the nature. In this world, all things will continue to deliver, utilize and afterward disposed in a super fast space. On the off chances that everyone make no trial to change to green option now, instantly to come, they will be accompany by the contamination and poison brought by the creation, utilization and arranging these non green product. The green business would additionally not be economical in the sense of there is little interest for re-cycle item. What is more they will likewise confront a genuine lack of asset and vitality, in turn the fact that much of these assets and vitality would have been squandered in driving non-vitality effective supplies and delivering new material and thing. Therefore, it is important to cope as a main concern on the utilization of eco accommodating item which permit everyone to reduce the negative impacts that is made when restrain the earth.

2.1 Perceived Product Price

Perceived pricing is defined as the assessment of a product and facility as indicated by the number of purchasers; who are passionate to pay for it, instead of the generation and conveyance costs. Utilizing a perceived quality valuation system depends on the degree of discretionary; however, it will support the viable advertising of a product since it sets items estimating in accordance with its perceived esteem to the potential purchaser. Ali and Ahmad (2012) and Fraj and Martinez (2006) emphasize that consumers may equip with sufficient knowledge and concern about natural environmental issues, but they are still sensitive regarding the price and quality of a particular green product. It shows that the price and quality of traditional products may be more important to a certain segment of consumer; hence, it may have impact on the natural environment.

According to the research work done by Delaney (2008), perceived product price is of the key factors that influence the purchase intention and buying behavior of consumers. In support, Yoneda (2010) avers that price is an integral component to the market competitiveness of a green product relative to traditional products. Thus, review of relevant studies identifies price as an important variable to shape consumer intention to purchase green products.

H1: There is a significant relationship between perceived price and green products purchasing intention.

2.2 Perceived Product Quality

According to Dodds (2003), quality can be characterized as incredibleness or predominance. In more detail, perceived quality can also be explained as the judgment from a customer towards a product. Perceived quality is not the same with the genuine quality and this is the presumption of the customer for a product and the capacity of a brand in order to satisfy his or her desires. It may or may not have relationship with the real incredibleness of an item, and it is studied together with the open picture of association and brand, experience of customer from the company's different product, and the impact will reflect to the supposition pioneer, shopper and so on (Gan et al, 2008).

In a conventional setting, Worthington (2013) claims that consumers are often held back by product price and the perception of product quality; however, in green product purchase, these two elements may play integral role to improve consumers purchase intention.

H2: There is a significant relationship between perceived quality and green products purchasing intention.

2.3 Advertisement Endorsement

Advertisement endorsement is a main factor that will affect consumers' purchase intention towards green product. Advertisement endorsement can influence and change consumers' perception, knowledge and attitude environment and green product. In addition, the traditional product and practice will have some impacts to the level of awareness of an environment (Apejoye, 2013). Green product always endorsed by advertiser by using popular celebrities. According to Gan et al (2008), consumers always draw the practices of popular celebrities and then make purchase decision according to their purchase intention, which remains under the influence of advertisement.

According to Petley (2003) study the advertising is a non particular type of advancement that is conveyed through chosen a media outlet. In some circumstances, it requires the advertiser to pay for message arrangement. Moreover, advertising has long ago to be seen as a system for mass advancement in a solitary message which can achieve a huge number of individual. Therefore, Ali and Ahmad (2012) claim that this mass advancement methodology causes some issues since numerous laid open of the advertising message and may not be in line with the plan and objective of the business. Hence, it may lead to the wasteful utilization and limited time reserve.

According to Roll (2005), marketing endorsement defined as a fundamental thought to getting the statement about the item or facility. There are three categories of marketing endorsements. First, marketing endorsement can be found from real companion, family, associates and someone who really know the interpersonal skill. Second, this is the one that the associations can get an endorsement from an outsider, as long as they are considered to have validity (Yoneda, 2010). Contemplate the audits the association has perused online where they do not know the commentator. Third, related to endorsement, from the outsider who has some manifestations of suasion over devotees.

H3: There is a significant relationship between advertising endorsement and green products purchasing intention.

2.4 Moderator Variable: Environment Knowledge

According to Ali and Ahmad (2012), environmental knowledge and attitude may not influence consumers' buying decision where green products are concerned. Contrary to this, Promotosh and Sajedul (2011) argue this notion with the fact that the purchase intention of a consumer is directly influenced by the likelihood that the consumer will purchase a product, which is tagged as eco-friendly.

According to Ali and Ahmad (2012) and Fryxell and Lo (2003) state the environmental knowledge is defined as a general knowledge of fact, concept, and relationship that concerning the natural environment and its major ecosystem. Environmental knowledge includes public knowledge which is the key relationship pertaining to environmental facet or impact (Ali, Ahmad, 2011). In a research, Promotosh and Sajedul (2011) investigated that environmental knowledge plays important role in creating intention of consumers to purchase green products. Therefore, it can be concluded that a consumer level of environmental knowledge will affect green product purchase intention.

H4: Environment knowledge moderates the relationship between perceived price and green products purchasing intention.

H5: Environment knowledge moderates the relationship between perceived quality and green products purchasing intention.

H6: Environment knowledge moderates the relationship between advertising endorsement and green products purchasing intention.

2.5 Green Products Purchase Intention

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By considering all these constraints and findings, this study developed a conceptual framework to assess of the effect of the three determinants on the purchase intention of green products. Figure 1 illustrates the conceptual model that has been created for the purpose of this study.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

3. Methodology

To achieve the objectives, this study mainly focused on primary data that had been collected by a structured close-ended questionnaire. The data was collected from public in Klang Valley areas. The respondents of this study were selected based on non-probability based sampling technique. A total of 180 respondents were selected as the sample size which is consisting of 30 respondents for pilot test and 150 respondents for the analysis from Klang Valley. The respondents are those user or potential user of green product in Malaysia. The respondents were diversified from the different background such as age, gender, education level and so on.

The questionnaire was designed in close ended format, which were based on various sources. For the part A in this research, the questions were designed based on nominal scale measurement. The questions consist of demographic profile of the respondents such as age, gender, income and so on. The reason to design this part is that to help in identifying the personal information related to their background. For the part B, this research uses internal scale to gather the dependent variables and independent variables. There are numerous different of issues can be used the measurement of five-point Likert scale such as social environment, environmental concern, social media, self-image, price sensitivity, quality consciousness, and brand consciousness. Furthermore, Cronbach's alpha was used to check the reliability of the data (Hair et al, 2010). In accordance with the outcome of the reliability from Cronbach's alpha, it can be seen that the scale in which the reliability is in from 0.743 to 0.890. Therefore, it is safe to say that the results have achieved acceptability reliability. This was adequate and deemed to be sufficient for conducting further analysis for this study. Finally, to achieve the objectives of the study, Multiple Regression Analysis and Pearson's Correlation Matrix has been used to identify the structural relationships among the constructs identified and to test the hypotheses.

4. Results and discussion

Data analysis is done by three ways, first demographic analysis, and then correlation and regression analysis is made. Demographic analysis is used to provide demographic characteristics of respondents. In addition, e-mail method is adopted to gather data from the sample of 150 participants; all participants were cooperative; hence, the response rate was 100%. For the study at hand, the dispersion of the gender for the survey was 49%, there is a large number of respondents belonging to a single age group i.e. 25-31years. It also shows that majority of respondents belongs to the same educational and income level and about 73% of respondents currently use green products or have intention to use it in future. Within this, 59% of respondents were female while the remaining 41% were males. According to the research of Larsson and Khan (2011) gender differentiation have no impact on the purchase intention of green products. Therefore, gender has no impact on the purchase decision of green products. The respondents in the age group of 25-31 are fresh graduates and newly employed respondents. Hence, they are expected to have more knowledge of using green products. Within this category about 79% were employed respondents. 9% were self-employed and others represent a very small share in survey. Majority of the respondents (57%) have a university degree of which, 20% are undergraduate and 9% of respondents are masters' degree holder. For the respondents income distribution, 67% of respondents earn MYR 1000-3,999, 17% of respondents earn less than MYR 1000 and the others earn more than that. The survey results show that about 84% of respondents are earning up to MYR 3,999

Correlation determines the relationship between two variables. Pearson correlation is a technique to determine the extent and direction (positively or negatively related) of relationship between the two quantitative variables. It ranges from +1 - -1. The lesser the relation the better it is because if any strong relation exist among variables it may produce wrong and inaccurate results. The relation should be less than 0.5 (Lehman, 2005).

Regression analysis is a process of determining relationship among variables, the effect of one variable over other. It studies, if independent variable changes what change it will bring in dependent variable and what is the relation between them (Cottrell, 2011). The summary of regression test is shown below in the table:

Table 1: Regression Test

	Hypothesis 1 Perceived Price	Hypothesis 2 Perceived Quality	Hypothesis 3 Advertising Endorsement
Beta	0.128	0.063	0.126
t-stat	1.737	0.922	1.889
p-value	0.085	0.358	0.061
Observations	144		
Durbin Watson	1.559		
Adj-R-square	0.195		
F-Value	9.685**		

Notes: Significance at the 5 per cent and 1 per cent level of confidence as indicated by * and ** respectively.

The value of beta shows the relationship between the two variables and p-value and t- values are used to determine the level of significance. In the above table perceived price is found to be positively related as the value of beta is 0.128 which means that any change in price will positively change the purchase intention of customers by 12.8%. P-value is 0.085 which is greater than .05 so the relationship between price and purchase intention is insignificant. The result is in contrast with the hypothesis as according to hypothesis there is significant relationship between perceived price and purchase intention. According to work done by Ansar (2013) there is significant positive relation of price with purchase intention, similar results are obtained by Morel and Kwakye (2012). Whereas the research of Larsson and Khan (2011) concluded that there is no relation between price and purchase intention. Therefore the results shown above accept the null hypothesis that is there is no significant relationship between price and purchase intention.

Perceived quality is also found to be positively related with the value of .063 which shows that any change in quality will bring change in purchase intention by 6.3%. P-value is found to be 0.358 which is greater than 0.05, it shows that there is insignificant relationship between the two variables, this also rejects alternative hypothesis that is there is significant relationship between quality and purchase intention. According to the study of Morel and Kwakye (2012), Choi and Kim (2013) there is positive and significant relationship between perceived quality and purchase intention of customers.

Advertising endorsement is also found to be positively related as the value of beta is 0.126 which indicates that any change in advertising will bring positive change in purchase intention. P-value is found to be 0.061 which is greater than .05 therefore the relationship between the two variables is statistically insignificant; this is also in contrast with the alternative hypothesis which says there is positive and significant relationship between the two variables. According to studies of Zhu (2013), Morel and Kwakye (2012), Ansar (2013), there is positive and significant relationship between the variables. Qader and Ziauddin(2010) also studied the similar relation between advertising and purchase intention; according to them advertisements have a positive and strong relationship with purchase intention of buyer. Advertisement encourages respondents to purchase a specific product. Effectiveness of advertising depends upon the marketing skills of company.

Hypothesis 4- Environment Knowledge Moderates Relation between Price and Purchase Intention

The table below shows the moderator effect of environmental knowledge on the relationship of perceived price purchase intention of customers:

Table 2: Moderator's effect on Price and Purchase Intention

Independent Construct	Purchasing Intention (Hypothesis 4)	
	block 1 (before moderating)	block 2 (after moderating)
	unstandardized coefficient	unstandardized coefficient
Constant	3.162 (11.766)**	2.553 (8.011)**
Perceived price	0.281 (4.484)**	0.190 (2.850)**
Moderation effect	-	0.234 (3.306)**
R ²	0.122	0.062 (R ² change)
F-value	20.107	10.928 (F change)
p-value	0.00	0.00

Notes: Significance at the 5 per cent and 1 per cent level of confidence as indicated by * and ** respectively.

Environmental knowledge is used as a moderator and the effect of this moderator on relationship between three variables that are price, quality and advertisement with purchase intention is discussed. In the above diagram Environmental knowledge moderates the relationship between price and purchase intention. Two scenarios are discussed, in block 1 moderator is not applied but in block 2 when moderator is applied it enhances the relationship between price and purchase intention by 23.4%. the relationship between price and purchase intention is found to be positive as discussed in table 4 and this relationship is further strengthened when moderator is applied. This result also accepts the alternative hypothesis which says environmental knowledge moderates the relationship between price and purchase intention. The result also shows the impact of price on purchase intention which is 12.2% with a change of .062 which means that moderator further enhances the impact price on purchase intention of customers.

According to the research of Larsson and Khan (2011), economic knowledge has a significant impact on purchase decision of customers for making purchase of green products. The more knowledge a customer has regarding the benefits and prices of green products, they will be more encouraged to purchase green products and will make repeated purchases.

Hypothesis 5- Environment Knowledge Moderated Relation between Quality and Purchase Intention

The table below shows the moderator effect of environmental knowledge on relation of quality and purchase intention of customers:

Table 3: Moderator's Effect on Quality and Purchase Intention

Independent Construct	Purchasing Intention (Hypothesis 5)	
	block 1 (before moderating)	block 2 (after moderating)
	unstandardized coefficient	unstandardized coefficient
Constant	3.315 (13.644)**	2.715 (8.953)**
Perceived quality	0.244 (4.331)**	0.153 (2.475)*
Moderation effect	- -	0.232 (3.148)**
R ²	0.115	0.057 (R ² change)
F-value	18.760	9.911 (F change)
p-value	0.00	0.00

Hypothesis 6- Environment Knowledge Moderates Relation between Advertisement and Purchase Intention

Environmental knowledge is used as a moderator variable and it is affecting the relationship between advertising endorsement and purchase intention. The moderator effect is shown in table below:

Table 4: Moderator's Impact on Advertisement and Purchase Intention

Independent Construct	Purchasing Intention (Hypothesis 6)	
	block 1 (before moderating)	block 2 (after moderating)
	unstandardized coefficient	unstandardized coefficient
Constant	3.224 (12.693)**	2.576 (8.209)**
Advertising endorsement	0.265 (4.331)**	0.18 (2.886)**
Moderation effect	- -	0.237 (3.318)**
R ²	0.124	0.063 (R ² change)
F-value	20.262	11.011 (F change)
p-value	0.00	0.00

Above table shows the impact of environmental knowledge on the relation of advertising endorsement and purchase intention of green products. When the moderator is applied in block 2 it enhances the relationship between the two variables by 23.7%. The value of R² is found to be 0.124 which shows that any change in advertising endorsement will change the purchase intention by 12.4%, R² change shows the change that has occurred by the application of moderator and it is 0.063 which means that R² have changed by 6.3% by the use of moderator. The result also rejects the null hypothesis and is consistent with the alternative hypothesis which says environmental knowledge moderates the relationship between advertisements and purchase intention of green products by customers.

According to the research conducted by Rehman and Dost (2013) environmental knowledge have no impact on purchase decision of green products, Rehman and Dost's research findings are similar to the statistical result conducted in Malaysia. However, this statistical finding totally contradict from what was found by Ali and Ahmad (2012) who stated that there is significant relationship between and consumer purchase intention on green products as environmental

knowledge includes public knowledge which is the key relationship pertaining to environmental facet or impact. This would indicate that environmental knowledge cannot stand alone in influencing consumers to purchase green products in Malaysia, however in other countries

4. Discussion

Correlation test shows that no strong relation exist among different variables, if strong relation exist between the variables the results may be vague and inaccurate as each of the variables will be affecting each other and in that some of the variables have to change in order to determine the accurate results. As weak relation is found among variables so regression test is performed on the regression equation and it was found that perceived price, perceived quality and advertising endorsement is positively related with purchase intention but the relationship is found statistically insignificant which rejects the alternative hypothesis. The result is not only in contrast with the hypothesis but also with the results obtained by Ansar (2013), Kwakye (2012), Larsson and Khan (2011), Choi and Kim (2013), Zhu (2013). The reason for these contrasting results may be the number of respondents, the research is based on the survey of 150 respondents only and majority of respondents belong to the same demographic group as discussed above, if the sample size is large or if survey is conducted covering different demographic segments the results may be more clear and accurate.

Hence the research found three hypotheses statistically insignificant and other three statistically significant. The results obtained by regression test are shown below:

1. There is positive but insignificant relationship between perceived price and purchase intention.
2. There is positive but insignificant relationship between perceived quality and purchase intention.
3. There is positive but insignificant relationship between advertising endorsement and purchase intention
4. Environment knowledge moderates relationship between perceived price and purchase intention.
5. Environment knowledge moderates relationship between perceived quality and purchase intention.
6. Environment knowledge moderates relationship between advertising endorsement and purchase intention.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

According to literature, recent years have witnessed considerable shift in the purchase behavior and intention of consumers, in Malaysia and across the world. In accordance with the literature, the research finds that consumers' intention to purchase green products seem to be under the influence of various factors.

Furthermore the attribute of price is observed to influence the behavior of the consumer over the period of time that initiates a motion of purchase in consumer behavior. According to the observation of data analysis it has been found significant that if there is decreases in price level of the green products deployed in the market the consumers are likely buy more of these goods that further brings goodwill to the society in terms of awareness of such healthy products among the consumer market (Henson, 2004).

In addition according to the survey it has been concluded that at the current stage when many of the other products then green products are deployed in market and the market has become saturated due to complexity and consumer is found confused in between selecting the right product for his usage. It is then found essential that such green product carry their products as prominent in order to bring awareness among the consumer market by uplifting the quality scale of the product which further pushes the consumer behavior in adopting such products and becoming brand loyal to such products which add value to their society by the nature of their usage as healthy and effective for the environment. The findings of this study are found significant in promoting such goods as worth using moreover another very important aspect of marketing this product is promoting these products via advertisement, which can be utilized by several techniques. According to marketing techniques it has been found essential if the company promoting such brand use celebrity brand endorsement in order to bring awareness among respondents related to such products which eventually increase the sales of these products. Reasoning being obvious fact is present, at the current stage if a company uses brand endorsement such as celebrity presence at the products promotional campaigns or producing advertisement on commercial lane in order to bring awareness via effective word of mouth has been the utmost priority of such companies Geller, (2009).

Another essential aspect within marketing such nature of products is the price of the products by analyzing the facts of such products it is found essential the company coats a price that is much convenient and feasible for the consumer market, this according to the survey information requires much awareness spread among the consumer market about the product moreover there has been found the negligible impact of the price coated and consumer perceived prices. This is again linked with the pricing strategy adopted by the company itself. It has further been found that many of the aspects are there in market who wishes to crack the market of green products that relates to the perceived quality of the

consumers that further pushes the sales. Within this context advertising techniques are found beneficial for the promotion of this product that is linked with the value added within the products which delights the consumer market and further pushes them towards the repurchase intention with regard to the green products.

References

- [1] Alwitt, L.F. and Pitts, R.E. (1996). Predicting purchase intentions for an environmentally sensitive product. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, Vol. 5 No. 1, pp. 49-64.
- [2] Aman, A., Harun, A. and Hussein, Z. (2012). The Influence of Environmental Knowledge and Concern on Green Purchase Intention: The Role of Attitude as a Mediating Variable, *British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 7(2).
- [3] Anderson, D., Burham, K. and Thompson, W. (2000). Null Hypothesis Testing: Problems, Prevalence and an Alternative, *Journal of Wild Life Management*, 64(4).
- [4] Anonymous (2010). Green products: Using sustainable attributes to drive growth and value Sustainable business solutions. Retrieved June 20, 2014 from <http://www.pwc.com/us/en/corporate-sustainability-climate-change/assets/green-products-paper.pdf>.
- [5] Anonymous (2014), Data Analysis. Retrieved June 20, 2014 from <http://learntech.uwe.ac.uk/da/Default.aspx?pageid=1409>.
- [6] Ansar, N. (2013). Impact of Green Marketing on Consumer Purchase Intention, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4 (11).
- [7] Azizan, S.A.M. and MohdSuki, N. (2013). Consumers' Intention to Purchase Green Product: Insights from Malaysia, pp. 1129 – 1141. Malaysia, IDOSI Publications.
- [8] Banyard, P. and Flanagan, C. (2005). *Ethical Issues and Guidelines in Psychology*. Routledge.
Borkar, R. (2011). Types of Social Influence. Retrieved July 12, 2014, from <http://www.buzzle.com/articles/types-of-social-influence.html>
- [9] Bui, M. and Loyola, H. (2005). Environmental marketing: a model of consumer behaviour..
- [10] Chan, R.Y. K. (2001). Determinants of Chinese Consumers' Green Purchase Behaviour. *Psychology and Marketing*, Vol. 18(4): 389–413
- [11] Cheah, C. M. (2009). A study on consumer's green purchasing intention. Master's thesis. Malaysia: College of Business, University Utara Malaysia.
- [12] Choi, E. and Kim, S. (2013). Consumer Purchase Intentions, *International Journal of Smart Home*, 7 (1).
- [13] Cochran, W.G. (2007). *Sampling Techniques*. 3rd ed. India: Wiley Pvt Ltd.
- [14] Cohen, J., West, S.G, Cohen, P., and Aiken, L.S. (2013). *Applied Multiple Regression/Correlation Analysis for the Behavioural Sciences*. Routledge.
- [15] Cooper, D. R. and Schindler, P. S., (2011) *Business Research Methods*. 11th Edn. McGraw Hill, 746 pages.
- [16] Cottrell, A. (2011), *Regression Analysis: Basic Concepts*. Retrieved June 20, 2014 from <http://users.wfu.edu/cottrell/ecn215/regress.pdf>.
- [17] Delaney, K. (2008). *Clean Home Green Home: The Complete Illustrated Guide to Eco-Friendly Home keeping*. Globe Pequot.
- [18] Deloitte (2009). Finding the green in today's shoppers: Sustainability trends and new shopper insights, pp. 4 – 26. U.S.A.: GMA.
- [19] Denscombe, M. (2007). *The Good Research Guide*. 3rd ed. McGraw-Hill International.
- [20] Dobson, A., and Lucardie, P. (Eds.). (2002). *The politics of nature: Explorations in green political theory*. Routledge.
- [21] Dodds, B. (2003). *Managing customer value: Essentials of product quality, customer service, and price decisions*. University Press of America.
- [22] Elham, R. and Nabsiah, A. W. (2011). Investigation of green marketing tools' effect on consumers' purchase behavior. *Business Strategy Series*, Vol. 12 Iss: 2, pp.73 – 83

- [23] Ferrante, J. (2012). *Sociology: A Global Perspective*. 8th ed. Cengage Learning.
- [24] Gratton, C. and Jones, I. (2010). *Research Methods for Sports Studies*. 2nd ed. Taylor and Francis.
- [25] Jackson, S.L. (2010). *Research Methods: A Modular Approach*. 2nd Edn. Cengage Learning.
- [26] Jackson, T. (2002). *International HRM: A Cross Cultural Approach*. SAGE Publications.
- [27] Larsson, S. and Khan, M. (2011), A Study of Factors That Influence Green Purchase. Retrieved June 20, 2014 from <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:614312/FULLTEXT02.pdf>.
- [28] Lee, C. H., Heng, Y. L., Jian, A. Y. and Hasan, M. A. (2012). Assessing Determinants of Green Purchase Intention, pp. 25 – 30. Malaysia: Multimedia University.
- [29] Lee, K. (2008). Opportunities for green marketing: Young consumers. *Marketing Intelligent and Planning*, 26, 573-586. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02634500810902839>
- [30] Lehman, A. (2005), *JMP For Univariate and Multivariate Statistics: A step by Step Guide*, Cary, NC.
- [31] Loux, R. (2008). *Easy Green Living: The Ultimate Guide to Simple, Eco-Friendly Choices for You and Your Home*. Rodale.
- [32] Madu, C. (2001). *Handbook of Environmentally Conscious Manufacturing*, pp. 190 – 199. U.S.A.: Kluwer Publishers.
- [33] Matas, A. and Jorgen, S., (2011). Generating research questions through problematization. *Academy of management review*, 36(2), pp:247-271.
- [34] Morel, M. and Kwakye, F. (2012), Green marketing: Consumers' Attitudes towards Eco-friendly Products and Purchase Intention in the Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sector. Retrieved June 20, 2014 from: <http://umu.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:553342/FULLTEXT01.pdf>.
- [35] Nejati, M. and Nejati, M. (2010). *Global Business and Management Research: an international journal*, pp. 323 – 335. U.S.A.: Universal Publishers.
- [36] Nizam, N.Z., Mansor, N., Mukapit, M. and Yahaya, S.N. (2011). Factors Influencing Customers' Decision To Buy Green Product Design in Malaysia, pp. 362 – 368. Malaysia: University Technical Malaysia Malacca.
- [37] Ottman, J. (1992a). Sometimes consumers will pay more to go green. *Marketing News*, pp. 6-16.
- [38] Ottman, J. (1992b). *Green Marketing: Challenges and Opportunities for the New Marketing Age*, NTC
- [39] Petley, J. (2003). *Advertising*. Black Rabbit Books.
- [40] Polonsky, M. J. (1994). An Introduction To Green Marketing. *Electronic Green Journal*, 1(2)
- [41] Preston, M. (2009). *Practically Green: Your Guide to Ecofriendly Decision-Making*. F+ W Media, Inc.
- [42] Price and Oswald (2008), Reliability of Measurement. Retrieved June 20, 2014 from <http://psych.csufresno.edu/psy144/Content/Measurement/reliability.html>
- [43] Promotosh, B. And Sajedul, I. M. (2011). Young Consumers' Purchase Intentions of Buying Green Products A study based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour Retrieved July 12, 2014, from <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:427264/FULLTEXT02> [14th June.14]
- [44] Qader, I. and Ziauddin, Y. (2010). Intention to Purchase Green Electronic Products: The Consequences of Perceived Government Legislation, Media Exposure and Safety and Health Concern and the Role of Attitude as Moderator, *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 1 (4).
- [45] Rehman, Z. and Dost, M. (2013). *Conceptualizing Green Purchase Intention in Emerging*
- [46] Rezai, G. (2007). *Factors Influencing Public Intention towards Purchasing Green Foods In Malaysia*, pp. 1- 20. Italy: University Putra Malaysia.
- [47] Roll, M. (2005). *Asian brand strategy: how Asia builds strong brands*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- [48] Saunders, M.N., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2011) *Research Methods for Business Students*. 5th edn. India: Pearson Education.
- [49] Shah, S. S. H., Aziz, J., Jaffari, A. R., Waris, S., Ejaz, W., Fatima, M., and Sherazi, S. K. (2012). The Impact of Brands on Consumer Purchase Intentions. *Asian Journal of Business Management*, 4(2), 105-110.

- [50] Shrikanth, R. and Raju, D.S. N. (2012) Contemporary Green Marketing – Brief Reference to Indian Scenario. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Interdisciplinary Research*, Vol.1 No. 1, January 2012, ISSN 2277 3630
- [51] Silverman. M. (2004) Non-Financial Recognition, The Most Effective of Rewards? Institute for employment studies.
- [52] Tanner, C., and Kast, S. W. (2003), Promoting sustainable consumption: determinants of green purchases by Swiss consumers. *Psychological Marketing*, 20, 883-902. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/mar.10101>
- [53] Tehrani, N. and Sinha, S. (2011). *Understanding Green Business*, pp. 320 – 331. U.S.A.: Author House.
- [54] The Star (2008, May 3). Malaysians produced enough garbage to fill 42 Petronas Twin Towers. Retrieved Jun 12, 2014, from <http://thestar.com.my/news/story.asp?file=/2008/5/3/central/21088304&sec=central>
- [55] Vazquez-Brust, D.A. and Sarkis, J. (2012). *Green Growth: managing the transition to a sustainable economy*, pp. 290 – 295. U.S.A.: Springer.
- [56] Vasil, A. (2012). *Ecoholic: Your guide to the most environmentally friendly information, products and services in Canada*. Random House LLC.
- [57] Wilson, A., and Piepkorn, M. (Eds.). (2013). *Green Building Products: The Green Spec™ Guide to Residential Building Materials--*. New Society Publishers.
- [58] Yoneda Y (2010). 6 Inspiring Examples of Groundbreaking Green Technology. Retrieved July 12, 2014, from <http://inhabitat.com/6-inspiring-examples-of-groundbreaking-green-technology/>
- [59] Zhu, B. (2013). the Impact of Green Advertising on Consumer Purchase Intention of Green Products, *World Review of Business Research*, 3(3).